

Milestone: M3.4 Creation of a Citizens hub

Lead Participant: Sciensano

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Due: 31/01/2026

Date Of Completion:

Means of Verification

Regarding Task 3.4 (The creation of a Patient and citizen hub) a first version of the citizen hub is live. The first version of “Let’s talk genomics – A toolkit for citizen engagement” can be consulted at <https://raixir.github.io/oneplusmg-trust-framework/lets-talk-genomics/>. The website already provides an overview of the topics that will be covered , as well as a (preliminary) glossary, a list of useful engagement initiatives and materials, and some general background information. All topics already include a short summary. Two topics (“At birth” and “Managing vulnerability”) have already been developed more in depth.

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

The website has been built and developed in strong collaboration with Task 1.3 (Project communication strategy and support to 1+MG). The overall structure of the website and the draft texts were provided by Sciensano (Task 3.4). The design and technical development of the website, as well as the review of the texts, were carried out by participants of Task 1.3. The initial ideas and some snapshots of the website were already presented to participants of Task 3.4 for preliminary feedback.

Next action steps

The website will not yet be widely disseminated, but will be shared selectively with a limited group of project participants, partners and potential users. Based on their feedback, the website will be adjusted where needed and further developed:

- In-depth development of all topics
- Continued expansion of the Glossary and the Overview of engagement initiatives and materials
- Bug fixing and website optimisation

Once the website is fully developed, dissemination activities will be a key priority.

